

Appendix 2: PESTEL analysis of the political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors impacting energy citizenship at the EU level

After establishing the list of the PESTEL letters-main factors (25) and the factors within each letter (97 in total), it seemed necessary to assess the weight of those factors in the support and/or development of ENCI at the EU level. To do so, two tools that belong to the multi-criteria decision-making (MDCM) have been adopted here: The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Decision-Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL) methods. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method was implemented to identify the most important factors and subfactors impacting ENCI. However, the AHP method could not identify the influence among the factors, since it is lacking in knowing the interrelationship among factors. To solve this, it is completed with the Decision-Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL) method. The objectives of this study are to identify the most impacting factors by determining the interrelationship between the factors and by identifying the influences of each factor to other factors. Considering the number of subfactors, the DEMATEL method was only implemented at the letters- main factors level (*i.e.* P, E, S, T, E, L), whilst the AHP method also addresses the various factors within each letter (P1-P5, Ec1-Ec5, S1-S4, T1-T4, En1-En3, L1-L4).

The following table shows the results obtained with the AHP method after treatment of the input of the 7 expert pairwise assessments (of which one had to be removed due to inconsistency while filling the assessment matrix)

HIERARCHISED FACTORS IMPACTING ENCI IN THE EU-CONTEXT (AHP)						
RANK	 Legal					
1	P2. Agreed upon climate and energy policy targets with current strategic developments	EC2. Steering the European economy through market intervention	S3. Social attitudes towards energy transition	T3. EU choices for integrated approaches towards energy efficiency	EN1. Climate change and climatic conditions	L1. Legal framings and specific enhancement of ENCI forms
2	P3. Commitments to participative governance	EC3. Design of and access to financing and investment EC5. Spatial distribution of economic activity	S4. Social and individual behaviour and habits	T1. EU technological choices towards decarbonisation of the energy sector	EN3. Environmental damages (pollution, emission, threat to biodiversity)	L2. Energy market-related rights (& duties) of consumers, prosumers and new producers

3	P5. Empowerment policies	EC1. Energy prices	S1. Social standing (education, occupation, income and status)	T2. Technological pathways for European T&D infrastructure	EN2. Energy related resources (geological, geographical)	L3. Legal recognition of and measures dedicated to vulnerable consumers, energy poverty & social inclusion
4	P1. EU-level political unification in the energy sector	EC4. Economic growth	S2. Demographic factors	T4. Digitalisation of the Energy System		L4. Legal uncertainties
5	P4. Non-governmental initiative towards energy transition					

Overview of the AHP and DEMATEL rankings

AHP Ranking*	DEMATEL D+R**	DEMATEL D-R***
1. Social	1. Economic	1. Political
2. Political	2. Political	2. Legal
3. Environmental	3. Social	3. Economic
4. Economic	4. Environmental	4. Social
5. Legal	5. Technological	5. Technological
6. Technological	6. Legal	6. Environmental

* In the AHP method, each factors are considered independently

** (D + R) represents the degree of importance each PESTEL letter plays in the entire system. In other words, (D + R) indicates both the factor's impact on the whole system and the factors system's impact on the factor.

*** (D-R) represents the degree of influence of a letter/factor on the system. In general, the positive value of D-R represents a causal variable, and the negative value of D-R represents an effect.